

Political Implications of Islamic Financial Instruments for Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria

Abdulbasit Kolapo Imam

Department of Politics and Governance
Faculty of Humanities, Management and Social Sciences
Kwara State University, Malete
abdulbasit.imam@kwasu.edu.ng

Abstract

This study explores the political implications of Islamic financial instruments on poverty alleviation policies in Nigeria, focusing on the roles of Zakat, Waqf, and Sukuk. Despite Nigeria's significant Muslim population and persistent poverty challenges, the integration of these faith-based financial tools into national poverty reduction strategies remains understudied. The research employs a qualitative, exploratory approach, utilizing document analysis and secondary data review to examine the complex interplay between religious principles, political decision-making, and poverty reduction strategies. Drawing on social contract theory and institutionalism, the study provides a comprehensive theoretical framework for understanding how Islamic financial instruments are incorporated into Nigeria's secular governance structures. The research investigates the influence of these instruments on policy formulation and implementation, the roles of political and religious institutions in their integration, and the associated challenges and opportunities. Findings reveal that Islamic financial instruments have the potential to significantly enhance Nigeria's poverty alleviation efforts by mobilizing resources, promoting financial inclusion, and supporting sustainable development initiatives. However, their effective implementation depends on political will, stakeholder collaboration, and public acceptance. The study identifies key challenges, including the need for a robust legal and regulatory framework, and opportunities, such as leveraging technology for improved fund management. This research contributes to the ongoing dialogue on integrating Islamic finance principles into secular political frameworks for poverty alleviation. It offers valuable insights for policymakers, development practitioners, and researchers, potentially informing more effective and inclusive poverty reduction strategies in Nigeria and other countries with significant Muslim populations.

Keywords: Islamic Finance, Poverty Alleviation, Nigeria, Zakat, Politics

INTRODUCTION

The interplay between religious principles, public policy, and socio-economic development has been a subject of extensive scholarly discourse, particularly in regions with diverse religious demographics like India, Cambodia, and parts of Asia and Africa (Haynes, 2007, p. 102). As the world grapples with the persistent challenge of poverty, the intersection of faith-based financial instruments and poverty alleviation strategies has gained significant attention among policymakers, development practitioners, and academic researchers. This research explores the political implications of Islamic financial instruments on poverty reduction policies, using Nigeria as a case study.

Globally, the role of religion in shaping public policy has been well-documented, with various faith-based traditions influencing the design and implementation of development programs. In the case of Islamic finance, the principles of Sharia law have given rise to a range of financial instruments, such as Zakat (obligatory almsgiving), Waqf (endowment), and Sukuk (Islamic bonds), that have the potential to contribute to poverty alleviation efforts (Obaidullah, 2008). These instruments, rooted in Islamic teachings' ethical and social responsibilities, offer alternative pathways for addressing socio-economic challenges, particularly in Muslim-majority countries. Zakat has a strong humanitarian and social-political value and occupies a central role in Islamic fiscal policy and operations. Islam provides its own comprehensive approach to how the state can raise revenue and how it should be spent. Zakat is collected from those who are qualified and distributed to the eight recipients as identified in the Quran (Surah At-Tawbah 9:60). Waqf instruments play an important role in Muslim societies, supporting the aged, the poor, and orphans through the provision of education, training, and business activities (Abdul Razak, 2019). The creation of Waqf is strongly advocated, especially the creation of cash Waqf in view of the expensiveness of land as Waqf. There are collaboration efforts for cash Waqf and Zakat collection being done through Islamic banks and Takaful.

Poverty remains a pervasive global issue, with a total of 712 million people globally living in extreme poverty, an increase of 23 million people compared to 2019 (World Bank, 2024b). Developing countries, especially in the Global South, have faced the brunt of this challenge, with sub-Saharan Africa accounting for the largest share of the world's extreme poor. In response, governments and international organisations have implemented a wide range of poverty alleviation strategies, ranging from cash transfer programs to infrastructure investments (Saidi et al., 2023). However, the effectiveness of these efforts has been limited, underscoring the need for innovative, context-specific approaches that leverage diverse resources and perspectives.

The integration of Islamic financial instruments into poverty alleviation policies represents one such innovative approach, with the potential to harness the transformative power of faith-based principles for social and economic development. Countries with sizable Muslim populations, such as Indonesia, Malaysia, and Bangladesh, have already made strides in incorporating Zakat, Waqf, and Sukuk into their national development strategies, with varying degrees of success (Diniyya, 2019). These initiatives have demonstrated the capacity of Islamic finance to mobilise resources, promote financial inclusion, and support sustainable development initiatives that target the needs of the poor and marginalised communities (Ahmed, 2007).

Nigeria, the most populous country in Africa and the continent's largest economy presents a unique case study in the intersection of Islamic finance and poverty alleviation (Umar & Saidu, 2020). As a country with a significant Muslim population, Nigeria has witnessed the emergence of state-level efforts to integrate Islamic financial instruments into poverty reduction programs, particularly in the northern regions where Islam is the dominant faith. The Nigerian government's issuance of Sukuk bonds to fund infrastructure projects also reflects a broader recognition of the potential role of Sharia-compliant financial tools in driving economic development and inclusive growth.

However, the political implications of these Islamic financial instruments on poverty alleviation policies in Nigeria remain understudied. Understanding the interplay between religious principles, political decision-making, and poverty reduction strategies is crucial for developing more effective and inclusive policies that cater to the diverse needs of the Nigerian population (Abdul-Majeed Alaro & Alalubosa, 2019). This research aims to shed light on this important intersection, exploring the ways in which Islamic financial instruments influence the formulation, implementation, and outcomes of poverty alleviation programs in the Nigerian context.

The study will delve into the specific roles of Zakat, Waqf, and Sukuk in shaping the political landscape and their impact on the design and execution of poverty reduction strategies. It will also examine the involvement of political and religious institutions in promoting and regulating the use of these instruments, as well as the potential challenges and opportunities associated with their broader adoption. The research aims to contribute to the ongoing dialogue on integrating Islamic finance principles into secular political frameworks. Through this examination, it offers insights that can inform more effective and inclusive poverty alleviation policies in Nigeria and potentially other Muslim-majority countries facing similar development challenges.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Despite the growing recognition of the potential role of Islamic finance in addressing socio-economic challenges, the political implications of these faith-based financial instruments on poverty alleviation policies remain understudied, particularly in the context of Nigeria (Raimi et al., 2010). As a country with a significant Muslim population, Nigeria presents a unique opportunity to understand how the integration of Islamic financial principles, such as Zakat, Waqf, and Sukuk, can shape the formulation and implementation of poverty reduction strategies (Abdul-Majeed Alaro & Alalubosa, 2019).

Poverty remains a persistent challenge in Nigeria, estimated to have reached 38.9% in 2023, with approximately 87 million Nigerians living below the poverty line as of 2023 (World Bank, 2024a). The Nigerian government has implemented various poverty alleviation programs and policies, including the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP) and the National Social Investment Program (NSIP). However, the effectiveness of these efforts has been limited, highlighting the need for a more comprehensive and inclusive approach to poverty reduction. The incorporation of Islamic financial instruments into Nigeria's poverty alleviation framework represents a potential avenue for enhancing the impact and sustainability of these initiatives. States in the northern regions of Nigeria, where Islam is the dominant religion, have already taken steps to integrate Zakat collection and distribution into their poverty reduction strategies, reflecting a blend of religious principles and political decision-making (Jum'at Dasuki, 2022). Similarly, the federal government's issuance of Sukuk bonds to fund infrastructure projects demonstrates a deliberate effort to leverage Sharia-compliant financial tools within the broader development agenda.

Despite these emerging trends, the political implications of Islamic financial instruments on poverty alleviation policies in Nigeria remain understudied. Understanding the interplay between religious principles, political institutions, and poverty reduction strategies is crucial for developing more effective and inclusive policies that cater to the diverse needs of the Nigerian population. This research aims to address this gap by exploring how Islamic financial instruments influence the formulation, implementation, and outcomes of poverty alleviation programs in the Nigerian context.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND OBJECTIVES

This research explores the political implications of Islamic financial instruments on poverty alleviation policies in Nigeria. To this end, the study will be guided by the following research questions and objectives:

Research Questions:

1. How do Islamic financial instruments, specifically Zakat, Waqf, and Sukuk, influence Nigeria's formulation and implementation of poverty alleviation policies?
2. What role do political and religious institutions play in integrating Islamic financial instruments into Nigeria's poverty alleviation framework?
3. What are the political challenges and opportunities in scaling Islamic financial instruments within Nigeria's national poverty reduction strategy?

Research Objectives:

1. To analyse the influence of Islamic financial instruments on the development and execution of poverty alleviation policies in Nigeria.
2. To evaluate the roles of political and religious institutions in promoting and implementing Islamic financial instruments in poverty alleviation efforts.
3. To identify the political challenges and opportunities in expanding the use of Islamic financial instruments for poverty reduction across Nigeria.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

In the context of this research, the key concepts that require clarification are Islamic financial instruments, specifically Zakat, Waqf, and Sukuk, as well as poverty alleviation policies within the Nigerian framework. Understanding the definitions and linkages between these concepts is crucial for analyzing their political implications on poverty reduction strategies.

Islamic financial instruments are a set of Sharia-compliant financial tools that operate based on the principles of Islamic law. Zakat is an obligatory almsgiving practice in Islam, where a percentage of one's wealth is required to be distributed to eligible recipients, often the poor and needy (Abdul-Majeed Alaro & Alalubosa, 2019). This religious obligation is grounded in the Islamic principle of social responsibility and the belief that wealth should be circulated throughout the community to promote equity and social welfare. The collection and distribution of Zakat are typically overseen by religious institutions or government agencies, making it a potentially powerful tool for poverty alleviation when integrated into public policy frameworks.

Waqf, on the other hand, refers to the Islamic endowment system, where assets are donated and held in trust to generate income for charitable purposes, including support for social welfare programs. Waqf assets can include land, buildings, or financial resources, and the generated income is used to fund initiatives such as education, healthcare, and infrastructure development (Haneef et al., 2015). This system of charitable endowments has a long-standing tradition in Islamic societies and has the potential to complement government-led poverty alleviation efforts by providing sustainable sources of funding for social programs.

Sukuk, often referred to as "Islamic bonds," are investment certificates that adhere to Sharia principles, such as the prohibition of interest and the requirement of asset-backing (Obaidullah, 2008). These financial instruments are used for fundraising purposes, including infrastructure development and other projects that can contribute to economic growth and poverty reduction. The issuance of Sukuk by governments or private entities represents a deliberate effort to leverage Sharia-compliant finance to mobilise resources for development initiatives.

In the Nigerian context, these Islamic financial instruments have gained traction in recent years, particularly in the northern regions where Islam is the dominant religion. Some state governments have incorporated Zakat collection and distribution into their poverty alleviation strategies, reflecting a blend of religious principles and political decision-making (Jum'at Dasuki, 2022). This integration of Zakat into public policy frameworks highlights the

potential for harnessing faith-based resources and practices to address socio-economic challenges, such as poverty. Additionally, the Nigerian federal government has issued Sukuk bonds to finance infrastructure projects, demonstrating a deliberate effort to leverage Sharia-compliant financial tools within the broader national development agenda (Oladunjoye, 2014). This move suggests a recognition by policymakers of the role Islamic finance can play in driving inclusive economic growth and improving the living conditions of the population, including the poor and marginalised communities.

Poverty alleviation policies in Nigeria encompass a range of government-led initiatives and programs aimed at reducing poverty and improving the socio-economic conditions of the population. These policies, such as the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP) and the National Social Investment Program (NSIP), have sought to address various dimensions of poverty, including income, access to basic services, and social protection (Ugwueze, 2023). The integration of Islamic financial instruments into these poverty alleviation frameworks represents an effort to harness the potential of faith-based principles and resources to enhance the effectiveness and inclusivity of these policies.

The linkages between Islamic financial instruments and poverty alleviation policies in the Nigerian context are multifaceted. Zakat, with its emphasis on obligatory almsgiving, can be leveraged to mobilise resources and direct them towards targeted poverty reduction programs, particularly in regions with significant Muslim populations. The Waqf system, with its longstanding tradition of charitable endowments, can provide sustainable funding for social welfare initiatives that address the needs of the poor. Moreover, the utilisation of Sukuk for infrastructure development and other economic projects can create employment opportunities and improve access to basic services, which are crucial components of holistic poverty alleviation strategies. The integration of these Islamic financial instruments into Nigeria's poverty alleviation framework reflects a recognition by policymakers of the potential synergies between religious principles and secular development goals. Harnessing the social and ethical dimensions of Islamic finance, the Nigerian government and state-level authorities aim to develop more inclusive and effective poverty reduction policies that cater to the diverse needs of the population, including those from Muslim communities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The integration of Islamic financial instruments into poverty alleviation strategies has garnered significant attention in recent years, particularly in Muslim-majority countries like Nigeria. This literature review examines the political implications of incorporating Zakat, Waqf, and Sukuk into poverty reduction efforts in Nigeria, exploring the intersection of Islamic finance, socio-economic development, and political decision-making.

Islamic finance instruments, particularly zakat, sadaqah, and waqf, present significant opportunities for addressing funding challenges in Nigeria, especially in the realms of humanitarian aid and education. The potential of zakat alone is remarkable, with estimates suggesting it could generate between USD 8,776.5 million and USD 21,160.99 million, which could substantially fill the humanitarian funding gap in the country (Lawal & Ajayi, 2019). This financial potential underscores the critical role that Islamic finance can play in alleviating poverty and supporting vulnerable populations, particularly in the Northeast region of Nigeria. The humanitarian crisis in Northeast Nigeria has been exacerbated by ongoing conflicts and economic instability, leading to a pressing need for effective funding solutions. Zakat, as a mandatory form of almsgiving in Islam, alongside sadaqah (voluntary charity) and waqf (endowment), can mobilise significant resources. For instance, if a weekly contribution of N20 is made, with a 5% cash collection error rate, it is estimated that approximately N162 billion could be generated annually through zakat and N106 billion through sadaqah, which could be

directed towards essential needs such as housing, healthcare, and food security (Lawal & Ajayi, 2019).

However, the effectiveness of these instruments is hindered by several challenges, particularly in Northern Nigeria. Public trust issues and inadequate management knowledge significantly affect the performance of zakat and waqf institutions. Research indicates that many potential zakat payers and waqf donors lack confidence in these institutions due to perceived corruption and mismanagement, particularly when political figures are involved in their administration (Ahmad, 2019). This lack of trust can deter individuals from contributing to these funds, thus limiting their potential impact. In the context of higher education, Islamic finance products such as sukuk (Islamic bonds), waqf, and zakat can provide sustainable funding solutions. The education sector in Nigeria faces severe financial constraints, and traditional funding sources have proven inadequate. Adewale and Zubaedy (2019) suggest that integrating Islamic finance into higher education funding could support the development of facilities, research, and student welfare. Their qualitative research highlights the need for collaboration among government entities, private investors, and Islamic finance experts to create a sustainable funding model that utilises these instruments effectively.

The legal framework surrounding sukuk in Nigeria is evolving, presenting new opportunities for infrastructure financing. As the government seeks to diversify funding sources, improved legislation and public awareness campaigns are essential to enhance the effectiveness of zakat and waqf institutions (Adeagbo, 2021). Such initiatives would not only bolster public confidence but also facilitate better management practices within these institutions. To maximise the potential of Islamic finance in Nigeria, a multi-faceted approach is required. This includes enhancing public awareness about the benefits of zakat, sadaqah, and waqf, developing robust legal frameworks, and fostering collaboration between various stakeholders. By addressing these challenges, Islamic finance can significantly contribute to alleviating the humanitarian crisis and improving educational funding in Nigeria, ultimately fostering sustainable development and economic empowerment for its citizens (Lawal & Ajayi, 2019; Adewale & Zubaedy, 2019).

Islamic finance has the potential to significantly enhance financial inclusion in Muslim-majority countries, including Nigeria, which is crucial for poverty alleviation efforts. Despite the growth of financial sectors in many Muslim nations, financial inclusion remains low, with only 27% of individuals and firms having access to financial services (Zulkhibri, 2016). This gap is attributed to various obstacles, including religious beliefs, which often deter individuals from engaging with conventional financial institutions.

Research by Akhter et al. (2019) highlights the positive impact of Islamic banking on financial inclusion, particularly in terms of borrowing. Their study, which analyzed data from middle and lower-income countries in Asia and Africa, found that Islamic banking plays a significant role in increasing demand for financial services among underserved populations. This suggests that Islamic financial instruments can effectively address the needs of those who are often excluded from traditional banking systems. Islamic finance approaches financial inclusion through two main avenues: risk-sharing contracts and wealth redistribution instruments. Mohieldin et al. (2011) emphasise that risk-sharing contracts provide alternatives to conventional debt-based financing, while redistributive instruments such as zakat, sadaqah, waqf, and qard-al-hassan can help integrate religiously excluded populations into the formal financial system. These instruments not only promote social justice but also enable wealth transfer from those who have more to those in need, thereby fostering economic stability.

Despite the promising potential of Islamic microfinance, its current outreach is limited, accounting for only 0.5% of global microfinance (Zulkhibri, 2016). To improve financial inclusion, policymakers in Muslim countries must focus on developing regulatory frameworks and financial infrastructures that support Islamic finance instruments. This includes enhancing

public awareness and trust in these financial products, which can ultimately lead to greater participation from excluded populations. Leveraging Islamic finance could provide a pathway to enhance financial inclusion in Muslim-majority countries, addressing both economic disparities and the unique needs of underserved communities. This approach not only aligns with the principles of social justice inherent in Islam but also supports broader economic development goals (Mohieldin et al., 2011; Zulkhibri, 2016).

Political Implications and Islamic Finance

The integration of Islamic finance into poverty alleviation strategies in Nigeria is a complex process that requires navigating the country's evolving political landscape. The legal framework for Sukuk, an Islamic financial instrument, is still developing, reflecting the ongoing efforts to accommodate faith-based financial tools within Nigeria's secular state structure (Adeagbo, 2021). This process involves political negotiations and policy-making to ensure that Islamic finance can effectively contribute to poverty reduction efforts. One key aspect of this integration is the role of government in managing Islamic social finance institutions, such as Zakat (mandatory almsgiving) and Waqf (endowment). Dasuki (2022) suggests that establishing dedicated government organs could enhance the effectiveness of these institutions, implying a shift in the traditional roles of religious and state institutions. However, this recommendation also highlights the delicate balance required in managing the intersection of religious institutions and political governance, as potential Zakat payers and Waqf donors may be wary of political office holders' involvement in the appointment of administrators (Ahmad, 2019).

Despite the potential benefits, several challenges hinder the effective implementation of Islamic financial instruments for poverty alleviation in Nigeria. Public trust issues and inadequate management knowledge are significant factors that limit the effectiveness of Zakat and Waqf institutions in Northern Nigeria (Ahmad, 2019). The lack of public trust and confidence in these institutions can be attributed to perceived corruption and mismanagement, particularly when political figures are involved in their administration. Moreover, the integration of Islamic finance into poverty alleviation strategies faces additional challenges, such as a lack of awareness and understanding about Islamic microfinance among the general public and policymakers (Alaro & Alalubosa, 2019). This lack of awareness hampers the adoption and integration of Islamic microfinance into mainstream poverty alleviation programs. Additionally, a shortage of skilled human resources with knowledge of both Islamic finance and microfinance makes it difficult to establish and manage Shari'ah compliant microfinance institutions effectively.

The legal and regulatory framework governing Islamic finance in Nigeria also presents challenges. Alaro and Alalubosa (2019) highlight the inadequate legal and regulatory framework to govern the operations of Islamic microfinance in Nigeria, leading to uncertainties and difficulties in its implementation. The absence of a comprehensive legal and regulatory framework that aligns with international best practices creates an unfavorable environment for the growth of Islamic finance in the country.

To overcome these challenges and harness the potential of Islamic finance for poverty alleviation, several recommendations have been put forth. Dasuki (2022) emphasises the need for increased government involvement in managing Zakat and Waqf institutions, suggesting that establishing dedicated government organs could enhance their effectiveness. This recommendation implies a shift in the traditional roles of religious and state institutions, potentially leading to new forms of collaboration and governance structures.

Furthermore, awareness campaigns and capacity-building programs are crucial to educate stakeholders, including the poor, about the benefits and workings of Islamic finance (Alaro & Alalubosa, 2019). Promoting collaboration between Islamic finance institutions,

government agencies, and development partners can leverage resources, expertise, and networks for effective poverty alleviation. Additionally, encouraging the use of Zakat and Waqf funds to provide concessionary financing and social services to the poor through Islamic microfinance institutions can significantly contribute to poverty reduction efforts.

While the reviewed literature provides valuable insights into the potential of Islamic financial instruments for poverty alleviation in Nigeria, several gaps in research remain understudied. While some studies touch on political aspects, there is a lack of in-depth analysis of the political implications of integrating Islamic finance into poverty alleviation strategies. Future research could explore how these instruments influence political decision-making, policy formulation, and governance structures. For instance, the work of Kuran (2004) on the political economy of Islamism provides a theoretical foundation for understanding potential tensions when integrating religious principles into secular frameworks. However, this perspective has not been extensively applied to the specific context of Islamic financial instruments in Nigeria's poverty alleviation efforts. The reviewed literature primarily focuses on the Muslim population. Future research could explore the perspectives of non-Muslim citizens and policymakers on the integration of Islamic financial instruments into national poverty alleviation strategies.

The literature review reveals a growing body of research on the potential of Islamic financial instruments for poverty alleviation in Nigeria. These instruments, including Zakat, Waqf, and Sukuk, offer promising avenues for addressing funding challenges in various sectors, from humanitarian aid to education. However, their integration into poverty alleviation strategies is fraught with political implications that require careful consideration.

The reviewed studies highlight the significant potential of these instruments to generate substantial funds for poverty alleviation efforts and enhance financial inclusion. They also underscore the challenges in implementation, including issues of public trust, management inefficiencies, and the need for appropriate legal and regulatory frameworks. The political implications of integrating these faith-based financial tools into secular governance structures are profound, touching on issues of financial inclusion, resource mobilisation, and the delicate balance between religious principles and state policies.

As Nigeria continues to grapple with persistent poverty, the strategic integration of Islamic finance into poverty alleviation efforts, guided by informed political decision-making and robust research, could play a crucial role in addressing this challenge. However, this integration must be carefully managed to ensure inclusivity, transparency, and effectiveness in poverty reduction efforts. Synthesising insights from the fields of Islamic finance, poverty alleviation, and political economy, this study aims to contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of how faith-based financial tools can be strategically integrated into secular political frameworks to address the persistent challenge of poverty.

This research will fill this gap by conducting a detailed examination of how these Islamic financial instruments are incorporated into the country's poverty alleviation policies, the dynamics between political and religious institutions in their governance, and the political challenges and opportunities associated with their broader adoption. Furthermore, the study will contribute to the ongoing dialogue on integrating Islamic finance principles into secular political frameworks. Analyzing the Nigerian case, the research will offer insights that can inform more effective and inclusive poverty alleviation policies in other Muslim-majority countries facing similar development challenges. The findings can guide policymakers, development practitioners, and religious institutions in navigating the complex interplay between faith-based financial tools and political decision-making to enhance the impact of poverty reduction efforts.

METHODOLOGY

This research adopted a qualitative and exploratory approach to investigate the political implications of Islamic financial instruments on poverty alleviation policies in Nigeria. The study employed document analysis and secondary data review to examine the complex interplay between religious principles, political decision-making, and poverty reduction strategies. The primary method of data collection involved a comprehensive review of secondary sources, including academic literature, government policy documents, reports from international organisations, and publications from Islamic financial institutions. These sources provided insights into the integration of Zakat, Waqf, and Sukuk into Nigeria's poverty alleviation framework.

Document analysis formed a crucial component of the research methodology. Official government publications, such as the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP) and National Social Investment Program (NSIP) documents, were analyzed to understand how Islamic financial instruments are incorporated into Nigeria's national poverty reduction strategies. Additionally, reports from state-level governments, particularly in the northern regions, were examined to assess the implementation of these instruments at the subnational level. The analysis also included a review of publications from Islamic financial institutions and regulatory bodies to gain insights into the country's governance and operational aspects of Islamic financial instruments. Academic publications were analyzed to provide theoretical foundations and comparative perspectives. The collected data was systematically analyzed using qualitative content analysis techniques, focusing on three main areas: the integration of these instruments into policy frameworks, the roles of political and religious institutions, and the challenges and opportunities associated with their broader adoption.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework for this research draws on social contract theory and institutionalism to illuminate the role of religion in public policy and governance, with a specific focus on the integration of Islamic principles into secular political frameworks for poverty alleviation.

Social contract theory, as developed by philosophers such as Rousseau and Locke, provides a foundation for understanding the relationship between the state and its citizens (Rousseau, 1762/1900). In the context of this research, social contract theory helps explain the legitimacy of incorporating Islamic financial instruments into poverty alleviation policies. It posits that citizens may accept or even demand the integration of religious principles into governance as part of the social contract, particularly in societies where Islam plays a significant role in shaping social norms and expectations.

Institutionalism, particularly the new institutionalism as articulated by scholars like North and Powell, offers a complementary theoretical perspective (North, 1990). This approach emphasises the importance of formal and informal institutions in shaping political and economic outcomes. In the context of Islamic financial instruments and poverty alleviation policies, institutionalism helps explain how religious practices and principles become formalised within governance structures and how they interact with existing secular institutions.

The institutional perspective is particularly relevant when analyzing how Zakat, Waqf, and Sukuk are integrated into Nigeria's poverty alleviation framework. It allows for an examination of how these Islamic financial instruments are adapted to fit within existing

institutional structures, as well as how they may reshape those structures over time. This theoretical lens also helps in understanding the roles of various institutional actors, including government agencies, religious organisations, and financial regulators, in the implementation and governance of these instruments.

Furthermore, institutionalism provides a framework for analyzing the potential challenges and opportunities in scaling the use of Islamic financial instruments within Nigeria's national poverty reduction strategy. It can help explain institutional resistance to change, as well as the conditions under which new institutional arrangements incorporating Islamic principles may emerge and gain legitimacy. Combining Social Contract Theory and Institutionalism, this research aims to provide a comprehensive theoretical framework for understanding the political implications of Islamic financial instruments on poverty alleviation policies in Nigeria. This approach allows for an analysis of both the normative justifications for incorporating religious principles into governance and the practical institutional dynamics that shape their implementation and impact.

FINDINGS

Comparative Lessons from Malaysia and Bangladesh

Malaysia and Bangladesh have successfully leveraged Islamic financial instruments for large-scale poverty alleviation, offering valuable lessons for Nigeria. In Malaysia, the effective utilisation of zakat and waqf has been pivotal in wealth redistribution and poverty alleviation. Zakat, a mandatory almsgiving, is collected from eligible Muslims and distributed among the eight categories of beneficiaries as outlined in the Quran. This system has been efficiently managed by the government and state religious authorities, ensuring that funds reach those in need. The use of waqf, particularly cash waqf, has also been instrumental in supporting the poor, orphans, and the elderly through education, training, and business activities (Abdul Razak, 2019). The success of these instruments in Malaysia can be attributed to strong government support, a robust legal framework, and effective collaboration between Islamic financial institutions, such as banks and takaful (Islamic insurance), and waqf organisations.

In Bangladesh, Shariah-compliant microfinance tools like Musharakah, Mudharabah, zakat, and waqf have been successfully implemented, providing financial inclusion to a large portion of the population. These instruments have proven to be viable and sustainable for launching micro-finance projects, which are critical in a country with a significant poverty rate. The success of these initiatives in Bangladesh is largely due to a supportive legal and regulatory environment that facilitates the operation of Islamic financial institutions (Abdul-Majeed Alaro & Alalubosa, 2019).

Integration of Islamic Financial Instruments in Nigeria

In Nigeria, the integration of Islamic financial instruments into poverty alleviation policies has been partial and remains a work in progress. Zakat has been identified as a potentially significant source of funds, with estimates suggesting it could generate between USD 8.8 to 21.2 billion, which is sufficient to address the humanitarian funding gap in the country (Lawal & Ajayi, 2019). Similarly, waqf has been proposed as a means to generate substantial funds for humanitarian needs, such as housing, healthcare, and education. For instance, if each telecom subscriber in Nigeria contributes N20 weekly, the total annual amount could reach approximately N106 billion (Lawal & Ajayi, 2019). Moreover, Sukuk, or Islamic bonds, are being considered for financing higher education and other infrastructure projects sustainably (Adewale & Zubaedy, 2019).

However, the integration of these instruments faces several challenges. The need for legislative acts to formally establish zakat and waqf institutions is critical for their effective collection and distribution. Furthermore, collaboration among government agencies, private investors, philanthropists, and experts in Islamic finance is necessary to overcome the funding challenges faced by higher education institutions and other sectors (Adewale & Zubaedy, 2019). Public awareness and acceptance of these instruments are also crucial, as widespread understanding of their benefits and mechanisms is essential for their successful implementation (Lawal & Ajayi, 2019).

The Role of Political and Religious Institutions

Political and religious institutions play crucial roles in promoting and regulating the use of Islamic financial instruments for poverty alleviation in Nigeria. Government agencies are encouraged to collaborate with private investors, philanthropists, industries, and Islamic finance experts to address the poor funding of higher education, which indirectly contributes to poverty alleviation (Adewale & Zubaedy, 2019). Additionally, the legal and regulatory frameworks must support the implementation of these instruments, ensuring they align with constitutional provisions on economic rights and financial inclusion (Abdul-Majeed Alaro & Alalubosa, 2019).

Religious institutions, including Islamic organisations and scholars, significantly influence the integration of Islamic finance into public policy. In Nigeria, religious stakeholders, such as Shariah experts, lecturers, and educational administrators, have advocated for the use of Islamic finance products like Sukuk, waqf, and zakat to achieve sustainable financing in higher education (Adewale & Zubaedy, 2019). The collaboration between political and religious institutions is essential for the successful implementation of these instruments, as seen in Malaysia, where such collaboration has facilitated the effective collection and distribution of funds (Hamzah, 2019).

Political Challenges and Opportunities

The scaling of Islamic financial instruments for poverty alleviation in Nigeria faces several political challenges. One major challenge is the lack of government commitment and effective policy implementation. Despite the various policies and resources dedicated to achieving the objectives of zakat and waqf, the realisation of these goals remains elusive, particularly in Northern Nigeria (Jum'at Dasuki, 2022). This gap between policy formulation and implementation underscores the need for stronger government commitment.

Another significant challenge is the absence of a robust legislative and regulatory framework. Lawal and Ajayi (2019) emphasise the need for legislation to formally establish zakat and waqf institutions, indicating that the current legal framework is inadequate for the effective utilisation of these instruments. Public awareness and acceptance also pose a challenge, as the success of these instruments depends on widespread understanding and support from the population (Lawal & Ajayi, 2019).

There is also potential political resistance from conventional financial institutions, which may view Islamic finance as a threat to their market share. The high-interest rates charged by local banks could be a point of contention as Islamic finance offers non-interest-based alternatives (Abdul-Majeed Alaro & Alalubosa, 2019). Additionally, the socio-political dynamics in Nigeria, a diverse country with various religious and cultural backgrounds, could lead to resistance in regions that are less familiar with or less receptive to Islamic financial instruments (Jum'at Dasuki, 2022).

Despite these challenges, there are significant opportunities for leveraging Islamic finance to enhance the effectiveness of poverty reduction programs in Nigeria. One major

opportunity is the potential for increased financial inclusion. Islamic non-interest microfinance options, such as *Mushārah* and *Mudhārah*, can ensure financial inclusion for a large percentage of Nigerians, aligning with constitutional provisions on economic rights (Abdul-Majeed Alaro & Alalubosa, 2019). Additionally, Islamic finance instruments like *zakat* and *waqf* have the potential to fill humanitarian funding gaps, with estimates suggesting that *zakat* alone could generate between USD 8.8 to 21.2 billion (Lawal & Ajayi, 2019).

Moreover, Islamic finance products such as *Sukuk*, *waqf*, and *zakat* can support sustainable development by providing facilities, scholarships, and research funding in higher education institutions, thereby contributing to the development of a skilled workforce (Adewale & Zubaedy, 2019). The roles of *zakat* and *waqf* in poverty eradication are also significant, as these instruments can provide a minimum means of livelihood for individuals, reducing poverty levels and contributing to national development (Jum'at Dasuki, 2022).

The findings highlight the potential of Islamic financial instruments for poverty alleviation in Nigeria, drawing on successful examples from Malaysia and Bangladesh. However, realising this potential requires addressing several political challenges, including the need for a robust legal framework, government commitment, public awareness, and overcoming potential resistance from conventional financial institutions. The collaboration between political and religious institutions is crucial for the successful implementation of these instruments, which have the potential to significantly enhance financial inclusion, humanitarian funding, sustainable development, and poverty eradication in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS & CONCLUSIONS

Based on the comprehensive analysis of Islamic financial instruments and their potential for poverty alleviation in Nigeria, several key recommendations and conclusions can be reached, some of which are the following.

Recommendations

The Nigerian government should prioritise the establishment of a robust legal and regulatory framework to support the implementation of Islamic financial instruments such as *Zakat*, *Waqf*, and *Sukuk*. This framework should clearly define the roles and responsibilities of various stakeholders, including government agencies, religious institutions, and financial organisations.

- Collaboration between political institutions, religious bodies, and the private sector should be encouraged and formalised. This multi-stakeholder approach can ensure the effective collection, management, and distribution of funds generated through Islamic financial instruments.
- A comprehensive public awareness campaign should be launched to educate Nigerians about the benefits and mechanisms of Islamic financial instruments. This initiative can help increase acceptance and participation across diverse socio-cultural groups within the country.
- The government should consider integrating Islamic financial instruments into existing poverty alleviation programs. This integration can enhance financial inclusion and provide sustainable funding for various sectors, including education, healthcare, and housing.
- Efforts should be made to leverage technology in the collection and monitoring of funds generated through Islamic financial instruments. This can improve transparency, accountability, and efficiency in fund management.

- Policymakers should explore the potential of Islamic non-interest microfinance options to enhance financial inclusion for a larger percentage of the Nigerian population, particularly those underserved by conventional banking systems.

Conclusions

The integration of Islamic financial instruments into Nigeria's poverty alleviation strategies presents a significant opportunity to address the persistent challenges of poverty and inequality. These instruments, particularly Zakat, Waqf, and Sukuk, have demonstrated potential to generate substantial funds for humanitarian needs and sustainable development. The success of implementing these instruments largely depends on political will, effective collaboration between various stakeholders, and public acceptance. While there are challenges, including potential resistance from conventional financial institutions and the need for a robust regulatory framework, the benefits of financial inclusion and sustainable funding for social development outweigh these obstacles. Experiences from countries like Malaysia and Bangladesh provide valuable lessons for Nigeria in effectively leveraging Islamic financial instruments for poverty alleviation. These lessons highlight the importance of government support, collaboration with financial institutions, and a comprehensive legal framework.

The political implications of integrating Islamic financial instruments into poverty alleviation strategies are far-reaching. They necessitate a delicate balance between religious principles and secular governance, requiring careful navigation of Nigeria's diverse socio-political landscape. Conclusively, the successful implementation of Islamic financial instruments can significantly enhance Nigeria's poverty alleviation efforts, promote financial inclusion, and contribute to sustainable development. However, this success is contingent upon strong political commitment, effective policy implementation, and broad-based public support. As Nigeria continues to grapple with poverty and inequality, the thoughtful integration of Islamic financial instruments presents a promising path towards a more equitable and prosperous future for all Nigerians.

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